

localization by the insect, thus preventing an erroneous sap intake from parenchymal tissues. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Studies on physiological aspects of drought in rice

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Different aspects of drought resistance in rice were studied in the field and greenhouse at IRRI.

The water-retention capacity at wilting stage of seedlings of different varieties ranged from 2 to 4.11 g/g dry matter. BR3 had the highest water-retention capacity and IR442, the lowest. Wilted seedlings of IR442 could hardly recover when watered.

When watered in the greenhouse 24 hours after wilting at the active tillering stage, the seedlings recovered from 32 to 72% of their length within 3 days. When watered 48 hours after wilting BR3 had the highest leaf-recovery efficiency and Katakara, the lowest. No variety recovered when watered 72 hours after wilting.

The wilting rates of rice varieties subjected to water stress developed by 1.5% NaCl at the active tillering stage varied widely.

When grown under prolonged desiccation in the field, BR3 gave the highest yield and Chandina the lowest. Root length development varied from 13 to 65 cm among varieties grown under moisture stress in polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipes.

A variety's drought resistance may vary under different conditions. Drought tolerance and drought avoidance mechanisms may be functions of separate genes. For example, in the PVC-pipe experiment, IR26 had higher resistance in terms of leaf tolerance for wilting, but

Soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica contents in rice varieties carrying different BPH resistance genes. IRRI, 1979.

Gene	Variety	Soluble silicic acid (mg Si/wet g)	Insoluble silica ^a	
			mg SiO ₂ /dry g	mg SiO ₂ /wet g
No gene	IR8	0.121	94	10.7
	IR20	0.113	106	11.0
	IR22	0.128	113	12.8
	IR24	0.121	104	11.4
	TN1	0.125	100	11.3
<i>Bph 1</i>	IR26	0.116	114	10.5
	IR2058-78	0.110	100	13.4
	Mudgo	0.115	97	10.8
	CO 10	0.109	112	14.9
	MTU15	0.101	116	13.4
<i>bph 2</i>	IR32	0.127	115	13.0
	H5	0.118	96	8.8
	H105	0.118	107	11.0
	CR94-13	0.125	114	11.4
	ASD7	0.106	91	11.6
<i>Bph 3</i>	Kuruhondarwala	0.110	112	11.4
	Gangala	0.109	107	10.8
	Rathu Heenati	0.120	105	11.4
<i>bph 4</i>	Heenhoranamawee	0.124	91	9.8
	Babawee	0.109	105	9.3
	Lekam Samba	0.096	91	10.6
	Kalukuruwee	0.103	107	11.2
	Kahata Samba	0.121	102	9.6
Unknown gene	PTB21	0.107	98	13.0
	PTB33	0.119	124	13.5
	Sudu Hondarwala	0.116	100	11.9
	Sinna Sivappu	0.114	91	11.8
	Balamawee	0.113	102	11.6
	Av	0.115	104.3	11.5

^aIn leaf sheaths after ethanol extraction.

its roots developed poorly and its ratio of root to shoot length was low. Dular and Mala were moderately tolerant of leaf wilting, although their avoidance capacity was high, as shown by their deep

root systems and high root-to-shoot length ratios. Therefore, evaluation for these two drought-resistance mechanisms should be separate. ■

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Deep water

Deepwater rice yields in Bangladesh

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Results of the first systematic assessment of Bangladesh deepwater rice yields in 1977 were described earlier (IRRN 35 October 1978). The study was continued in 1978.

Growth conditions for deepwater rice were generally favorable; inundation was later but more rapid, and water